

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF THE CURRENT STATE OF SYNTHETIC AND ANALYTICAL ACCOUNTING OF SECURITIES

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Abstract

The article deals with the problem of assessing the current state of synthetic and analytical accounting of securities. Since Azerbaijan gained its independence, favorable conditions have been created for the necessary reforms to integrate it into the world's economic system. The transition to a market economy has paved the way for the free movement of capital and financial resources. Undoubtedly, the formation of the Azerbaijani securities market and the application of international standards in their accounting play an important role in this direction. The author touches upon the current state of synthetic and analytical accounting of securities in Azerbaijan and the steps taken in recent years to improve it.

Keywords: market relations, financial investment, financial accounting of securities, synthetic accounting of securities, joint and dependent ventures, short and long term investments.

Reforms in the field of deepening market relations, which began with the restoration of Azerbaijan's state independence, have created favorable conditions for the development of the country's economy and greater integration into the world economic system. In such conditions, the formation of the national economy and the determination of the country's place in world markets, the strengthening of its position for the foreseeable future has become one of the priorities of political and economic policy of our state. Market economy is based on the diversity of property, the dynamics of supply and demand, increased competition, economic freedom, the transformation of profits into a driving force and the expansion of market infrastructure [1, p. 26].

The transition to a market economy has paved the way for the free movement of capital and financial resources. Every business entity engaged in entrepreneurial activity, in order to make more efficient use of the capital and financial resources within its competence, directs the remaining part of them in one form or another to large-scale reproduction, wants to make more profit by working, as well as social benefits.

Investment means the free use of free financial resources, real estate and intellectual property at the disposal, regardless of the form of ownership and organizational subordination, for large-scale reproduction with the purpose of gaining profit [2, s. 36]. Financial investments, being a type of assets of a commercial company, are funds invested in securities, interest-bearing bonds, authorized capital of other companies to boost economic efficiency and increase capital [3, p. 34]. Financial investments include:

- securities of state and municipal bodies, securities of other organizations, including debt securities (bonds, shares);
- investments in the authorized (share) capital of other organizations (including subsidiaries and independent economic entities);
- loans to other enterprises, deposits, receivables, etc [4, p. 95-96].

Investments in securities are considered financial investments and are long-term and short-term (not

more than one year) depending on the duration [5, p. 29]. Certain conditions are required for the securities to be reflected in the accounting records:

1. Official documents confirming the existence of the financial investment and documents confirming the receipt of funds arising from these rights (purchase agreement, extract from the register, etc.).
2. Transfer of financial risks related to financial investments to the owner (price change risk, debt repayment risk, liquidity risk, etc.).
3. Ability to bring economic benefits to the company (in the form of interest and dividends).

According to their nature and function, securities are divided into equity securities, debt securities and derivative securities. Equity securities are shares of other joint-stock companies acquired for the purpose of obtaining additional income or participating in the management of a joint-stock company [6, p. 66].

Debt securities include bonds, promissory notes and deposit certificates.

Synthetic accounting of securities is regulated by the rules of accounting in accordance with the International Financial Reporting Standards of January 30, 2017 of the Board of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Synthetic accounting of securities, according to the new chart of accounts, in the section of investments accounted for using the Participation Share method, 151st Investments in Dependent Enterprises, 152nd Investments in Joint Ventures, 153rd Depreciation of Investments in Joint Ventures adjustments to the account and other long-term financial assets section Long-term investments held to maturity 181, Other long-term investments 183, adjustments for impairment of other long-term financial assets 184 231-year Short-term investments held for sale, 232-year short-term investments held to maturity, 235-year Other short-term financial assets due to impairment, 311-year Issue income , 403 Long-term convertible bonds, 405 Long-term limited-term preferred shares (long-term), 407-year Subsidiary (dependent) Liabilities incurring short-term interest expenses, 505-year Recoverable limited-term preferred shares (short-term), 506-year Derivative (dependent) liabilities incurring short-term interest expenses, 532-

year Derivative (dependent) Short-term payables to enterprises are recorded in share accounts in the profits (losses) of subsidiaries and joint ventures.

Accounting for investments in associates is governed by IAS 28 Investment in Associate and Joint Ventures. When the shares are in the range of 20% – 50%, there is a main-parent and dependent enterprise relationship between the dependent enterprises. A subsidiary is an entity in which the investor has significant influence and is accounted for using the equity method. The amount invested in a subsidiary is recognized with initial cost. In this case, the following accounting statement is issued:

DT 151 Account of investments in dependent enterprises

KT 435, 445, 538, 545 accounts payable

Let's take a look at the cases in question, using the information from the organization whose materials are used. In January 2018, Anadolu Investment Company receives 95% of the shares of Azerbaijan Industry Insurance for AZN 10,450,000.

In this case, the following accounting transfer is issued:

DT 151 Investment account for subsidiaries 10,450,000

KT 223 Bank settlement accounts 10 450 000

As of December 31, 2018, Anadolu Investment Company reflects 40% ($500,000 * 40\% = 200,000$ manat) of the profits of Azerbaijan Industry Insurance in its reports. Anadolu Investment Company's profit or loss after the acquisition date increases or decreases the carrying amount of the investment. The amount of the share received is recognized in the statement of benefit or loss or other comprehensive income and the following accounting statement is made:

DT 151 Investment account for dependent enterprises AZN 200,000

KT 811 Share account in profits (losses) of subsidiaries and joint ventures AZN 200,000

If Anadolu Investment Company receives dividends from Azerbaijan Industry Insurance

DT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 50,000

KT 151 Investment account for dependent enterprises AZN 50,000

Anadolu Investment Company has recorded the loss of Azerbaijan Industry Insurance in the amount of AZN 300,000 at the end of 2018 as follows:

DT 811 Share account in profits (losses) of subsidiaries and joint ventures AZN 120,000

KT 151 Investment account for dependent enterprises AZN 120,000

DT 341 Net profit (loss) account for the reporting period is AZN 120,000

KT 811 Share account in profits (losses) of subsidiaries and joint ventures AZN 120,000

According to the fair value method, if there is an increase in the balance sheet of investments of associates, the transaction is recorded as follows:

DT 151 Account of investments in dependent enterprises

KT 611-2 Sub-account of income without revaluation

DT 611- 2 Sub-account of income without revaluation

KT 801 Share account in profits (losses) of subsidiaries and joint ventures

Under the fair value method, if there is a decrease in the balance sheet of investments of associates, the transfer is made as follows:

DT 731-2 Sub-account of expenses without revaluation

KT 151 Account of investments in dependent enterprises

DT 801 Share account in profits (losses) of subsidiaries and joint ventures

KT 731-2 Sub-account of expenses without revaluation

An investment in an associate classified as held for sale shall be recorded using the equity method from the date on which it is classified as intended for sale if it no longer meets this classification criterion. In this case, the following accounting entries are given:

DT 151 Account of investments in dependent enterprises

KT 231 Short-term investment account held for sale

When the investment in a subsidiary is repaid

DT 217 Other short-term receivables account

KT 151 Account of investments in dependent enterprises

When that amount is paid:

DT 223 Bank settlement accounts 47 account

KT 217 Other short-term receivables account

Investments in joint ventures are accounted for in the Number 152 asset account, which is governed by IAS 28 Investments in Dependent and Joint Ventures. According to the International Standard, two or more parties carry out jointly controlled economic activities through a Joint Action Agreement. In this case, the accounting records related to the transactions are made as follows:

When investing in joint ventures:

DT 152 Investment account for joint ventures AZN 300,000

KT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 300,000

When making a profit from a joint venture:

DT 152 Investment account for joint ventures AZN 5,000

KT 811 Share account in profits (losses) of subsidiaries and joint ventures AZN 5,000

Long-term investments held until payment are recorded in the account Number 181 recognized in IFRS 39 using financial instruments reflected in Standard IFRS 39 - Recognition and Measurement. This account is intended to record the existence and movement of long-term financial assets with a specified payment date and amount. Specifically, such investments include bonds, long-term securities, etc.

As an example, let's look at the business operations of an organization whose materials are used:

Anadolu Investment Company purchased 100 bonds of Azerbaijan Industrial Insurance with a unit value of AZN 1,000, duration of 5 years and an annual income of 5%. When obtaining 5-year bonds:

DT 181 Long-term investment account held before payment AZN 100, 000.

KT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 100, 000.

When interest income on bonds is recorded:

DT 176 Account of long-term receivables of debtors AZN 25,000

KT 442 Revenue account for future reporting periods AZN 25,000

When receivables of debtors accrued for the first year are classified as short-term receivables:

DT 216 Short-term receivables of debtors AZN 5,000

KT 176 9 Long-term receivables of debtors account AZN 5,000

Interest income accrued for the first year is transferred from long-term income to short-term income:

DT 442 The income account for future reporting periods is AZN 5,000

KT 542 The income account for future reporting periods is AZN 5,000

Interest income for the first year is recognized:

DT 542 Income account for future reporting periods AZN 5,000

KT 631-1 Interest income account AZN 5,000

Receivables of debtors included for the first year:

DT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 5,000

KT 216 Short-term receivables of debtors account AZN 5,000

After 5 years, the paid bonds:

DT 223 Bank settlement account AZN 100,000

KT 181 Long-term investments held until payment AZN 100,000

Accounting for short-term investments is recorded in the account of short-term investment №232 held until payment in accordance with №39 IFRS and №23 Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement Standard, approved by the decision №Q-01 of the Board of the Ministry of Finance on January 30, 2017. If the payment duration of financial investments previously classified as held-until-payment investments is received within 12 months after the reporting date, such investments are to be transferred to the account of №232 (short-term investments held until payment) from account №181 (long-term investments held until payment).

Anadolu Investment Company received 100 bonds with AZN 1000 unit value of Azerbaijan Industrial Insurance under the terms of one year and an annual income of 5%. Appropriate percentage must be paid to bondholders at the end of the year. Transactions are recorded as follows:

1. When obtaining 1-year bonds:

DT 232 Short-term investment account held before payment AZN 100,000

KT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 100,000

2. When recording interest income on bonds:

DT 35 216 Short-term receivables of debtors account AZN 25,000

KT 542 The income statement for the next reporting period AZN 25,000

3. When paying percentages:

DT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 5,000

KT 216 Short-term receivables of debtors account AZN 5,000

4. When recognizing interest income:

DT 542 The income account for future reporting periods is AZN 5,000

KT 631-1 Interest income account AZN 5,000

5. When repaying the bond after 1 year:

DT 223 Bank settlement account account AZN 100 000

KT 232 Short-term investment account held before payment AZN 100,000

Other long-term investments №183 account for the purchase of up to 20% or more than 50% of the shares of another enterprise. Purchases of more than 50% of shares are considered a subsidiary and up to 20% are considered ordinary investments. If Anadolu Investment Company acquires 70% of the shares of Azerbaijan Industrial Insurance:

DT 183 Other long-term investment account Azn 500,000

KT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 500,000

№184 – an adjustment to the impairment of other long-term financial assets is made to account for a decrease or increase in the value of a non-current financial asset as a result of a revaluation. Anadolu Investment Company has acquired 5% of the shares of Azerbaijan Industrial Insurance and is given the following accounting entry:

DT 183 Other long-term investment account AZN 200,000

KT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 200,000

In case of decrease in the value of purchased shares:

DT 731 Other operating expenses account AZN 10,000

KT 183 Other long-term investments 2 account AZN 10 000

If the asset is expected to be sold within 12 months after the reporting period, it is classified as a non-current financial asset. are taken into account.

Assets held for sale are revalued at fair value. The result of the revaluation of assets held for sale is recorded in the revaluation reserve account 331.

The disposal of such assets is included in the statement of comprehensive income. In the event of impairment on those assets, the accumulated negative revaluation surplus is recorded in the income statement. If Anadolu Investment Company buys 5,000 shares of Azerbaijan Industrial Insurance for a total of AZN 50,000 (AZN 10 per share), it is neither a dependent nor a subsidiary. Thus, these shares have been purchased for sale in the future:

In this case, when buying shares:

DT 231 Short-term investment account held for sale AZN 50,000

KT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 50,000

If the market price of one share of Azerbaijan Industrial Insurance increases and becomes AZN 11:

DT 231 Short-term investment account held for sale AZN 5,000

KT 331 Revaluation reserve account AZN 5,000

During the sale of shares (AZN 11):

DT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 55,000

KT 231 Short-term investment account held for sale AZN 55,000

When recognizing income from the sale of shares:

DT 331 Revaluation reserve account AZN 5000

KT 631-8 Other financial income sub-account AZN 5000

Account No. 311, Issue Income, is intended to reflect the issue income.

If the enterprises established in the form of a joint-stock company sell their shares at a price exceeding the nominal value at the time of creation of the authorized capital, the amount of the difference between the sale and nominal value of the shares is reflected in 311 Issue income and they are recorded in the following accounts.

311-1 Issue income sub-account Ordinary shares

311-2 Issue income sub-account Preferred shares

In order to regulate all these processes, in case of sale of shares, the difference between the sale price of shares and their nominal value, i.e. when the issue income is taken into account, the following accounting entries are made:

DT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 10,000

KT 311 Issue income account AZN 10,000

When an entity issues a convertible bond (debt security), it is recorded in account 403, which is a long-term convertible bond, if it has not been sold within 12 months of the reporting date.

Except for the right of enterprises to receive interest on convertible bonds, it is preferable to switch to other securities of the issuing joint-stock company (for example, shares) or newly issued shares or to purchase shares. Azerbaijan Industrial Insurance has issued long-term convertible bonds with a nominal value of AZN 1,000 and a total value of AZN 50,000, 15% per annum, convertible for a period of 3 years (subject to change within 3 years by the bondholders).

Let's take a look at the accounting records for that transaction:

1. In case of sale of convertible bonds:

DT 223 Bank account AZN 50,000

KT 403 Long-term convertible bonds account AZN 50,000

2. When accounting for interest expenses on bonds for the reporting period:

DT 751-2 Interest expense on convertible bonds sub-account AZN 7500

KT 3537 Short-term loan interest account AZN 7,500

3. When calculating interest expenses on the following year's bonds:

DT 191 Deferred expenses account AZN 15,000

KT 434 Long-term loan interest account AZN 15,000

4. A repurchase is a limited-term (long-term) preferred stock of a limited liability company that is repurchased for more than 12 months after the end of the reporting period, and the shares are recorded in account 405.

Preference share is a type of share, which, as a rule, gives the owner, regardless of the issuer's activity, a fixed percentage of the nominal value of the share after the liquidation of the issuer, as well as other issues

provided for in the issuance of shares and the issuer's charter [7, p.33].

In 2017, Azerbaijan Industrial Insurance issued 1,500 preferred shares worth of AZN 100. The term of the issued Preference shares is 2 years, after which these shares will be repurchased. Preference shares received a dividend of 5% per annum under the agreement.

In case of sale of preferred shares:

DT 223 Bank settlement account AZN 150,000

KT 15 405 Repurchased limited-term preferred shares (long-term) preference shares AZN 150,000

When calculating dividends on preferred shares during the reporting period:

DT 751-1 Interest expense sub-item AZN 7500

KT 537 Interest expenses short-term loan interest account AZN 7500

3. When dividend expenses on next year's preferred shares are taken into account:

DT 191 Deferred expenses AZN 7500

KT 434 Long-term creditor debt AZN 7500

4. In case of repurchase of preferred shares after two years:

DT 405 Preference shares with limited-term (long-term) account AZN 150,000

KT 223 Bank settlement accounts AZN 150 000.

In addition to the risk of default on future economic benefits, there are other financial risks involved in diverting existing funds to the securities of other entities. In the Financial Statements Report, a provision is made at the expense of profit to reduce the value of investments in securities in the event that the price of shares in the enterprise falls below the market value. This provision is recorded in the sub-account 414 of other long-term assessed liabilities on the depreciation reserve for investments in securities.

The created reserves are debited to the profit and loss account 341 and credited to the sub-account of the reserve account for the depreciation of investments in 414 securities. When the market price of securities increases in the initially created reserves account, the sub-account of reserves for impairment of investments in 414 securities is debited and the 341 profit and loss account is credited. The same procedure is used in the process of delisting securities previously created at the expense of relevant reserves.

Impairment inventories should be reviewed and reassessed at the end of each reporting year. In recent years, important steps have been taken to improve synthetic and analytical accounting of securities. Thus, in the new table of accounts, securities transactions are divided into current (short-term) and long-term. This distribution of financial investments is an integral part of the overall concept of asset accounting. Investments made during the year are easily distinguished from short-term investments. Long-term investments are investments made for more than a year.

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PERSONALIZATION OF SERVICES AND NEW TOOLS THAT AFFECT STANDARDS OF QUALITY IN THE SECTOR OF BEAUTY AND COMMERCIAL MEDICINE

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Abstract

This article discusses the basic principles of a quality management system, quality standards in service organizations, the purpose of which is to continuously improve the company's activities and increase their competitiveness. The article focuses on the problem of attracting new customers in the salons. One of the basic principles of the management system is customer orientation, customer capital. The paramount importance is the provision of high-quality cosmetic services with high-quality products using the algorithm "Personalization of the offer for new clients based on the digital technology".

Keywords: Cosmetic care, evaluation, purchase, entrepreneurs, paramount, personalization, commercial medicine, provision, innovative approach.

The range of services offered at small enterprises in the beauty industry is constantly expanding, innovative materials and processes are being introduced. As you know, small businesses in the beauty industry are able to quickly respond to changes in consumer demand, provide a quick return on costs and have great opportunities to implement an individual approach to customers. However, the problem of attracting new customers to the salons, as well as forming a permanent circle of customers, is still acute, which allows us to achieve sustainable profit growth.

"Customer orientation" is one of the main principles of the quality management system. The companies' customer capital consists of current and past customers who have interacted with the company and its products, as well as future subscribers who may be interested in offering it later. In this context, the ability to communicate and influence consumers is critical to the company's value creation and competitiveness processes, as well as to ensure its proper and sustainable functioning in the future. Consumer behavior can be defined as the process of making decisions that affect individuals and groups during the evaluation, purchase, use, and further disposal of goods and services (Brady & Cronin, 2001). By adapting their behavior to different customer groups, entrepreneurs can better meet the expectations of individual consumers and thus ensure their satisfaction and interest.

For the high-quality provision of cosmetic care, the quality of the doctor's work, the use of highly effective cosmetics and technical devices that can have a

positive effect on the disturbed physiological and biochemical processes in the skin due to various, including environmental factors are of paramount importance. The quality of the work of the doctor himself is determined by his knowledge and manual skills acquired in the process of implementing the medical service, analyzing its effect in the near and long-term observation periods. This is where the need for discussion arises: where it is appropriate to talk about medical technologies, and where it is appropriate to talk about standards (Behn, 2003).

The problem that exists in the service organizations (in the beauty industry) within the framework of the quality management system is the lack of proper orientation to the consumer (the consumer experience of customers, their feedback on previous visits to other beauty salons, insufficient personalization of the provided offer is not taken into account) (Scott & Odum, 2015). This problem can be solved by using the algorithm "Personalization of the offer for new customers", based on the use of a digital footprint and digital technologies.

The database available at enterprises contains a minimum set of information, including the last name, first name, patronymic, address, phone number and the number of requests for the service (not always). This does not allow you to track the "history" of the customer. The sites themselves are boring and monotonous, difficult to understand. Working with regular customers is reduced to providing discounts. There is no customer feedback. This is despite the fact that feedback from citizens is considered as "a key element of